

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Lesson on Russian Literature based on the communicative-activity approach (literary tale)

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the communicative-activity approach to the study of Russian literature by schoolchildren for whom Russian is not their native language. The article presents the experience of designing lessons for the study of the tale of O. Wilde and A. Pushkin. The examples of achieving performance in terms of skills and competencies, the implementation of integrated teaching of speech activity, a combination of types of educational activities are shown. The experience of didactics is generalized from the standpoint of motivation to study a second language and literature, and the formation of effective communication skills. The fairy tale "The Nightingale and the Rose" by O. Wilde is considered as a model of learning from the standpoint of enhancing the empathy of students, adapting the fairy tale to the perception of the listener. Communication exercises are developed using cultural linguistics, the development of the student's linguistic competence, the ratio of the communicative and pragmatic sides of the lesson, using the experience of textbooks in a fixed format. The development of the recommended didactic resource takes into account the directions of the reform in the secondary school of Kazakhstan. The method of practical teaching of literature is described from the standpoint of achieving measurable results, the implementation of text-centric teaching, integrated teaching of speech activity, a combination of types of educational activities, comparative study of English and Russian literary fairy tales. It has been substantiated that the practical task of teaching, the assessment of students' answers as an element of learning, contribute to their motivation to study a second language and literature, the development of critical thinking, and a creative approach.

Keywords: second language, didactics, literary tale, Pushkin, Wilde.

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Introduction

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The relevance of the article is due to the advantages of the communicative-activity approach in teaching the integrated subject - "The Russian language and literature" - to schoolchildren for whom Russian is not their native language. In the terminology of Kazakh didactics, the abbreviation L1 is adopted for schools with Russian language of instruction, and L2 for schools with a non-Russian language of instruction. Highlighting the practical task of learning makes demands on achieving performance in terms of skills and competencies, integrated teaching of speech activity, and a combination of educational activities. The following fairy tales were chosen as a didactic resource: O. Wilde "The Nightingale and the Rose" and A. Pushkin - "The Lukomorye has a green oak" (prologue to the poem "Ruslan and Lyudmila") and "The Tale of the Priest and His Worker Balda".

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of this article is to develop a lesson matrix in the aspect of achievable measurable results and an algorithm for the student's educational activity. The description of the methodology for the practical teaching of the Russian language and literature to schoolchildren (L2) required solving problems: 1) how to achieve measurable results, 2) how to implement text-centric learning, 3) why it is important to teach all types of speech activity, 4) how to differentiate and combine forms of educational activity, 5) how to carry out a comparative study of English and Russian literary tales.

Literature review

In the motivation for learning a second language and literature, scientists distinguish the mechanism of perception: curiosity and curiosity as "desire to know" and "state" (Fadle, Bialik, Trilling, 2017). Researchers also note the importance of the linguacultural approach: "The aim of language policy is not only to teach / learn a language for communication purposes, but also with the help of effective intercultural communication to support understanding and tolerance, respect for different cultures and identities. In order to implement cultural aspects into foreign language teaching, we need to understand the basic terms and relationships between them" (Reid, 2011, p. 20).

Methodological aspects of learning a second language are considered from the viewpoint of the formation of effective communication skills. Hence the role of speaking: "In light of the current global context, the notion that speaking ability has always been a source of instructional focus in the development of L2 proficiency and in classroom-based and high-stakes assessment instruments might seem intuitive" (Isaacs, 2016). The scientist writes about speaking as a factor of identity: "Speaking is a crucial language skill which we use every day to communicate with others, to express our views, and to project our identity" (Fan, Yan, 2020). To achieve effective communication, in addition to verbal ones, attention is drawn to the

performance of non-verbal actions by students: “People exist and interact with one another through multiple means of information, which is conveyed verbally or non-verbally” (Thuong, 2018, p.13). The following thought can be cited about the effectiveness of non-verbal feedbacks in the learning process: “Some people may even be more interested in such non-verbal feedbacks when they talk to others” (Thuong, 2018, p.14).

The examples of the use of the communicative-activity approach proposed in this article are in the nature of a recommended didactic resource in relation to the lessons of a textbook with updated content for grade 5 (Zhanpeys, Ozekbayeva, 2017). In the material of lessons dedicated to a foreign fairy tale Ch. Perrault, G. H. Andersen, the Brothers Grimm, and the tale of A. Pushkin with the integrated nature of the subject, grammatical tasks prevail. This, for example, is the composition of sentences using the accusative form of adjectives, the definition of their syntactic function. The activation of students' knowledge is achieved by assignments aimed at naming fairy tales based on the extracts given. The development of speech is based on the students' expression of opinions about the tales of Andersen and Perrault according to the proposed model of the beginning of the sentence. The writing task is a closed test showing correct and incorrect answers based on the writers' tale. The lesson on Pushkin's fairy tale includes information about the poet's biography without problematizing the material. The task is aimed at enhancing the activity of students: to recall the content of the fairy tale "Tales of the Fisherman and the Fish". Memories also relate to students' knowledge of adjectives, the ability to determine their gender using questions. Listening and speaking tasks involve students demonstrating their knowledge of the grammatical characteristics of adjectives.

Methodology

The methodological basis of the article is characterized by a generalization of the principles of the communicative-activity approach, which makes it possible to clarify the advantages of communicative didactics in comparison with the traditional approach aimed at forming a knowledge paradigm. The shift of the knowledge paradigm to the competence model, the development of competencies and skills required the use of heuristic methods, the use of cognitive scaffolds in the analysis of a work of art, and the description of methods of semantic reading of a text.

Results

The fairy tale "The Nightingale and the Rose" is interesting as a model of learning from the positions: activation of empathy of students, adaptation of a fairy tale with philosophical, aesthetic and social principles, the paradoxical nature of Wilde's work and the twofold nature of Pushkin's fairy tale to the perception of the listener.

The situational (communicative) exercises presented in the article are based on target attitudes (verbal actions of the teacher) and modeling situations for students. Motivation is formed in the system of speaking skills.

When developing communication exercises, the following requirements were methodologically defining: 1) a mechanism of motivation for learning a second language, 2) a culture-based approach, 3) development of a student's linguistic competence, 4) experience in using textbooks of a fixed format, textbooks navigators, 5) using a lesson-spread model (a single spread is a 2-page lesson), 5) compliance with regulatory requirements (in grade 5, three hours a week are allocated for the study of the subject), 6) the ratio of the communicative and pragmatic sides of the lesson, which explains the principles of selecting extra-linguistic and linguistic parameters for measuring the secondary linguistic personality, such as the pragmation, the reader's thesaurus. The development of communication exercises, or activity (hereinafter: ACT - UK, EG) for the analysis of Wilde's fairy tale "The Nightingale and the Rose" and the comparative study of Pushkin's fairy tale is aimed at activating imagination, memory, speech development and cultural competence.

In a comparative study, it is important to pay attention to the dual nature of the laughter (play) principle in Pushkin's fairy tale, which contributes to the understanding of the paradox. Another difference that catches the eye and characterizes the difference between Pushkin's fairy tale and Wilde is an adventurous beginning. Communication exercises are based on traditional teaching. The number of communication exercises per lesson is 5-6, the objectives of the lesson are from 1 to 3. The objectives of the lesson with the communicative-activity approach are formulated for the student in the form of measurable and achievable results. These results are differentiated from the standpoint of knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired in a specific lesson.

Discussions

Reform in the school of the Republic of Kazakhstan

Since 2015, the goal of teaching the subject "The Russian Language and Literature" at school has been the improvement of speech skills in the aspect of developing "functional literacy of students" (TipovayaUchebnayaProgramma, 2017/ Modal curriculum). The reformation in secondary school education (2018) led to the development of textbooks with updated content. PISA analysis in the field of reading literacy determined the recognition of the communicative-activity approach as a strategy that most effectively contributes to the achievement of practical learning goals.

Dialogue training is aimed at understanding someone else's statement, and the individual culture of artistic perception is assessed as an indicator of a versatile personality. The emphasis on the communicative-activity approach is also explained by the concept of four-dimensional education: in addition to knowledge, skills, personal qualities, a significant facet is meta-learning (teaching the ability to learn): "internal processes, how we conceptualize and adapt to learning" (Fadle, Bialik, Trilling, 2017, p. 169).

The reform was also caused by a new understanding of the effectiveness of training, which implies a shift in emphasis from the knowledge paradigm to the acquisition of skills and competencies. In other words, there is a problem of teaching productive speech actions. The practical task of teaching also ensures the continuity of learning at the next stage of education: "Due to the current conditions, more attention in the process of teaching students in higher education institutions should be paid to mastering language for specific purposes, focused on students' professional linguistic needs, fluency in a foreign language as a necessary means of intercultural communication in the educational, every day, scientific and professional spheres of life" (Klimova, Klimova, Dubinka, 2019).

The experience undertaken in this article has prerequisites in a number of works by one of the authors. Based on the material of the educational and methodological complex (hereinafter and everywhere: UMK - U.K., Y.G., A.A.) "The Russian language and literature for the 6th grade of a comprehensive school of Kazakhstan with a non-Russian language of instruction" (Urazayeva, 2018) justified the skills of schoolchildren - to create texts that provide communication, speak publicly, adapt to various speech situations, discovering the formed speech behavior, clearly, clearly formulate and argue the point of view, understand and analyze someone else's speech, read and accurately interpret texts, etc. In another article, the application of the communicative-activity approach is described on the material of the Russian Literature teaching and learning complex for the 7th grade of the Russian school (Suleimenova, Kozhamkulova, Urazayeva, 2018).

Application of the communicative-activity approach in school with L2

Note that the complexity of the development of modern textbooks lies in the strategy of including grammar tasks in the lesson with the integrated nature of the subject. Text-centered learning requires a synthesis of linguistic and literary assignments. No less important is the cultural component associated with the understanding of cultural differences. Text-centered learning is based on the analysis of key episodes, actions and deeds of the heroes, comparing the studied work with the literature of other peoples, as well as works of other types of art. In this article - due to the volume - communication exercises of a grammatical nature are not presented.

For schools with L2, the role of speaking is isolated. The implementation of verbal and non-verbal actions by schoolchildren characterizes the speech and communicative competence of schoolchildren. Reflection, which ends each lesson, is aimed at creating a certain product of communicative activity and may include non-verbal actions (stage performance, performance according to a script with musical and dance accompaniment). At this stage, the teacher checks not only the success of the students' consolidation of the acquired knowledge and skills, but also ensures the motivation of students to learn a second language.

Achieving the learning goal: assessing the statement (monologue / dialogue) from the point of view of its relevance to the proposed topic / situation - presupposes substantiating the opinion with understanding the evaluation criteria, which not only contributes to the development of teamwork skills, understanding the idea of shared responsibility for the success of the team This approach realizes the principle that assessment is an element of learning. The listing of selection criteria is an awareness of the requirements for the task. The importance of expressing one's own opinion, especially in writing, is due to the modern approach: "... that writing is a social act and a medium of individual expression over academic realm." (Sukandi, 2016). As the experience of learning English as a second language has shown, the role of writing for the holistic perception of the text and the transfer of understanding is of particular importance: "there was an indication of general resentments and strong feelings amongst the EFL students where the majority indicated that they are sometimes graded unfairly and writing assessment should take another, more holistic approach rather a narrow on "(Obeid, 2017, p. 174).

The choice of an English fairy tale in a comparative aspect with the Russian one is explained by the approach of the educational situation to inculturation. On the one hand: "Everyone knows people from deferent cultures have their own cultural perceptions, beliefs, aloes and social customs which greatly determine their communication ways, it is not surprising to find that people have many difficulties and obstacles in understanding one another and communicating with one another" (Zhang, 2010, p. 224). On the other hand, James Usher's concept of "stress-free language learning" is successfully solved when simulating game situations. This approach contributes to the development of students' skills in the context of effective intercultural communication: "The ability to prevent potential conflicts and foster productive, cooperative relations will depend largely on effective intercultural communications" (Samovar, Porter, McDaniel, Roy, 2013, p. 4). Another didactic problem is the concept of multilingual communicative intercultural competence, which is "an integrative phenomenon that ensures the correct, simultaneous and / or consistent use of several languages in multicultural communication" (Baryshnikov, Vartanov, 2018, p.11).

The transformation of fairytale canons in Pushkin's poetics consists in the emergence of a social genre with

a kind of humor and satire. As the researcher notes: "In Pushkin's fairy tales of the early 30s of the 19th century, the motive of" lack "is not clearly expressed, often instead of it there are intrigues and intrigues caused by envy" (Nikolsky, 2019). The influence of interpersonal relations, family conflicts becomes the object of the poet's satire. The importance of using strategies for the semantic reading of fairy tales is due to the search for the hidden meaning of Pushkin's fairy tales widely represented on the Internet. Agreeing that "the interpersonal relationships of the characters, their actions, vices (punished) and virtues (rewarded) are part of the cultural code of the Russian mentality" (Boris, 2019, p. 309), the author analyzes modern interpretations of images from Pushkin's fairy tales, among which are distinguished between legitimate and far from the source. The economic foundations of the relationship between the heroes in the tale of the priest and Balda (Gordienko, Lyutykh, Rudzitis, 2020, p. 57-58) may be of interest for modeling game situations. To understand the laughter principle and its dual nature, as well as the transformation of the fairytale canons, it is important to work with the satirical onomasticon and the methods of the etymology of the hero's name. Attention to vocabulary work and phraseological resources of the Russian language contributes to the development of students' vocabulary and understanding of Pushkin's humor.

O. Wilde's tale and peculiarities of study

The fairy tale of the English writer was studied in grade 5 schools from L2 according to the standard program until the 2017-18 academic year. For pupils of the 5th grade of a comprehensive school with L2, Wilde's tale in the context of updating the content of textbooks was replaced by the tales of C. Perrault and G.H. Andersen.

The paradoxical nature of the fairy tales of the English writer has led to their ambiguous interpretation by critics. Thus, in the Pall Mall Gazette, doubts were expressed about the ability of a children's audience to perceive Wilde's fairy tales with their decorative style, overloaded text with complex descriptions. Indeed, Wilde's theory of aestheticism is crucial for understanding his tale: "This helps us understand that Wilde believed in the supremacy of art to nature and even to morality" (Hafudh, 2017, p. 10), when the writer placed art above morality and nature.

Comparison of Wilde's tales with Andersen, recognition of the novelty of the tales of the English writer were accompanied by an indication that they were intended for an adult reader. Here we can cite the famous remark of the writer that both British children and the British reading public were his addressees. The success of Andersen's fairytales Swiss psychoanalyst M.L. von Franz explains neurosis, which "was not only his individual conflict, but also the conflict of the entire North" (Frants, 1998, p. 204). The researcher has in mind the problem of sex life, which terrifies a person, which is explained by "Christian hypocrisy

imposed from the outside", and the violent pagan temperament under "this puritanical corset." The difficulty of studying Wilde's tale is also explained by biblical mythology, in particular the idea of suffering and self-sacrifice.

An exception is the fairy tale "The Nightingale and the Rose". Common to the fairy tales of the English writer is the theme of imminent death. There is also a known version: "The Nightingale and the Rose" is interpreted as "a simple allegory of the destruction of love and beauty by materialistic civilization" (Seward, 1989), although there is a reference to the Persian legend. For the study of a fairy tale, the decisive thought is: "Wilde adopts nightingale's traditional artistic image as the singer of true love and the embodiment of truth, kindness and beauty" (Ping, 2018, p. 337). The exercises proposed in the article correspond to the author's concept of images about Nightingale as romance, and the Student and the girl as unworthy of romance (Clifton, 2004).

Communication exercises for studying the fairy tale by O. Wilde

Lesson 1.

Topic: Heroes of O. Wilde's fairy tale "The Nightingale and the Rose"

Lesson objectives:

By the end of the lesson, you will have learned:

- *about the heroes of the fairy tale "The Nightingale and the Rose",*
- *about the ways of expressing one's opinion.*

By the end of the lesson, you will be able to:

- *express attitude towards the heroes or their actions,*
- *use syntactic constructions to express your opinion,*
- *write a 5-minute essay.*

Call stage (5 minutes). Look at the pictures (see Figure 1-4). Imagine that you have flowers, a jar and a vase. How would you decorate the bouquet? Draw your bouquet. Describe the stages of work.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

How do you think this assignment relates to the topic of the lesson? Here, the learning goals are achieved: to present information in the form of pictures (hereinafter and everywhere the learning goals are indicated according to the standard program - UK, YG, AA), to predict the content of the text on the issues.

ACT 1. Listen (2 minutes)

The teacher's story about the creation of a fairy tale by O. Wilde. The author began by creating the form of the work, then strove to give it a grace of style. The goal of learning is achieved: to understand the general content of the text by identifying keywords and phrases.

ACT 2. Remember (10 minutes)

Questions and tasks:

Look at the pictures (see fig. 5 and 6). What legends and fairy tales are reproduced here? What do they have in common? Find a drawing with a similar plot or idea of a legend, myth, work and complete the row (Fig. 7). Prove that your example has a common plot or general idea with these images.

Figure 5

Figure 6

**FIND A PICYURE WITH
YOURS**

EXAMPLE

Figure 7

Here, on the basis of comparison, the ability to identify commonality and difference, justification of one's position is achieved. In other words, it is planned to achieve the learning goals here: to extract information on the proposed topic from various sources, to compare the content and topic of the texts.

ACT 3 Reading (5 minutes)

Read expressively by roles. Pay attention to the highlighted words.

<She said *she would dance with me if I bring her red roses*, - exclaimed the young Student, - but in my garden there is not a single red roses.

The Nightingale heard him, in his nest on the Oak, and, *surprised*, looked out of the foliage.

- *Not a single red rose in my whole garden!* - continued to complain

A student and *his beautiful eyes filled with tears*. - *Oh, what trifles sometimes depends on happiness!* I have read everything that wise people have written, I have comprehended all the secrets of philosophy, - and my life is broken just because I do not have a red rose. >

The learning goals are achieved: master the types of reading (introductory, commented), read by role. The consolidation of the studied material is carried out differentially in groups. Here the goal of learning is achieved: to present the main content of the text based on the listened, read and / or audiovisual material.

ACT 4. Discussing (8 minutes)

Questions and tasks:

Describe the heroes. Did the readers correctly convey the characters of the main characters? Expert opinions (brainstorming). The learning goals are achieved: to participate in a dialogue, correctly understanding the cues and providing feedback, to present the main content of the text based on the listened, read and / or audiovisual material. The next task is to work with a mental map. This task is aimed at achieving the goals: to understand the general content of the text, defining keywords and phrases, to present the main content of the text based on the listened, read and / or audiovisual material. The second part of the assignment is reflection: writing a 5-minute essay. However, preliminary work in groups is required to complete it.

ACT 5. I am a writer (5 minutes)

The task is carried out in groups.

1 group. Nightingale

2 group. Student

3 group. Daughter of the Professor

Each group selects three key words for a "trifle" and writes them down on a mental map, proving the position. Each group writes a five-sentence story on behalf of the hero in the form of an opinion, dream, or solution. Learning objectives: create a statement (description, narration) based on illustrations, comics, create texts (letter, diary, poem, fairy tale) using elements of colloquial and artistic styles.

AST 6. Let's evaluate the best essay (5 minutes)

Lesson 2.

Topic: Love is more precious than Life?

Lesson objectives:

By the end of the lesson, you will have learned:

- *about the idea of a fairy tale,*
- *about the ways of expressing one's opinion.*

By the end of the lesson, you will be able to:

- *express attitude towards the heroes or their actions,*
- *formulate the idea of a fairy tale,*
- *express an opinion and defend it.*

Call stage (5 minutes). Reception challenge. Each student writes in a notebook and names five associations that the word "precious" evokes in him. What are the real values for you? Why? This task can also be completed using the "Alley of Opinions" technique. Another option is to put anonymous notes with the names of the most valuable concepts or things in the "Opinion Basket" and discuss it in the class. Learning goal: to participate in the dialogue, correctly understanding the remarks and providing feedback; extract the necessary information on the proposed topic from various sources.

ACT 1 Reading and Discussing (5 minutes)

Read the text carefully. What do the highlighted words have in common?

“This is a real lover,” said the Nightingale. - What I was only singing about, he is experiencing in practice; what is joy for me is suffering for him. Truly love is a miracle. It *is more precious than an emerald and more precious than the finest opal. Pearls and pomegranates* cannot buy it, and it is not put on the market. You cannot sell it in a shop and you cannot exchange it for *gold* ›.

Questions:

Why is love more precious than all the listed stones?

Give an example to prove Nightingale's thought: "Truly, love is a miracle."

The peculiarity of the wording of questions in problem learning is the need for students to give detailed answers. Learning objective: to determine the main idea of the text based on the questions.

ACT 2. Draw a portrait of the Nightingale (6 minutes)

Questions and tasks:

For whom and why did the Student's tears and his suffering: “But with me she will not want to dance,

because I don't have a red rose for her" - caused a laugh?

How do you imagine these characters?

Describe the Nightingale's reaction. To complete the task, make a morphological analysis of the word "sacrament". Give synonyms to it. Make up one sentence each with the words "sacrament" and "mystery."

How do you imagine Nightingale?

Write three keywords in a notebook and, based on them, create a verbal portrait of him from three sentences.

Learning objectives: to retell the main content close to the text, create an utterance (description, narration), participate in dialogue, correctly understanding the lines and providing feedback.

ACT 3. Playing roles (7 minutes)

Questions and tasks:

Compose key words for retelling. Retell the role of the Nightingale's encounter with the three rose bushes using reference words and quotes.

This is where retelling skills are developed. Learning objectives: retell the main content close to the text, master the types of reading (introductory, commented), read by role. The retelling can be preceded by the teacher's words and the medieval legend that the nightingale is afraid of snakes and therefore does not sleep at night, clinging to a thorn: then he sings sadly because of the pain, except for the well-known ancient Persian myth about the love of a nightingale for a rose "in Lalla Rook Thomas Moore (Murray, 1979).

ACT 4. Meeting with the author (7 minutes)

Suggest a mind map. There are three words: Death - Life - Love. Combine the class into three groups and write out the keywords for each concept on the map, based on the text.

"Death is a dear price for a red rose," exclaimed the Nightingale. - Life is sweet to everyone! How nice it is to sit in the forest to admire the sun in a golden chariot and the moon in a chariot made of pearls. Sweet is the scent of hawthorn, lovely blue bells in the valley and heather blooming on the hills. But Love is dearer than Life, and the heart of some bird is nothing in comparison with the human heart! >.

Questions and tasks:

What does the fairy tale teach? Continue the sentence "A fairy tale teaches that ..."

Choose the best option. Rate it. Justify your choice. Write down your best offer.

Learning objectives: to analyze the content of small works of folklore and literature, defining the topic and the main idea, to present the main content of the text based on the listened, read and / or audiovisual material, to write creative works on literary topics, expressing your attitude towards the heroes of works of art or their actions with using epithets and comparisons.

ACT 5 Arguing with the author (10 minutes)

Unite into three groups. Give one argument "For" and "Against" the author's thought.

1 group. Love is dearer than Life.

2 group. Is love more precious than Life?

3 group. Experts. Who is right and why?

Learning objectives: to participate in the dialogue, correctly understanding the remarks and providing feedback, to evaluate the statement (monologue / dialogue) in terms of its relevance to the proposed topic / situation.

Lesson 3.

Topic: Usefulness and uselessness in art

Lesson objectives:

By the end of the lesson, you will have learned:

- *about the role of the images of the Student and the Daughter of the Professor,*
- *that love and art, according to Wilde, require sacrifice.*

By the end of the lesson, you will be able to:

- *express attitude to the author's thoughts about love for art,*
- *write a 5-minute essay.*

Call stage (10 minutes).

Unite into three groups. Give one argument each and show short presentations with evidence (this is homework). Continue the sentences.

1 group. Art is useful because ...

2 group. Art is useless because ...

3 group. Experts.

Swap groups. Provide new arguments.

Learning objectives: to participate in the dialogue, correctly understanding the remarks and providing feedback, to evaluate the statement (monologue / dialogue) in terms of its relevance to the proposed topic / situation.

ACT 1. (7 minutes)

Read the text. Pay attention to the highlighted words.

<The student got up from the grass, took out a pencil and a notebook from his pocket and said to himself on his way home from the grove: - Yes, he is *a master of form*, you cannot take that away from him. But does he have a feeling? I'm afraid not. In essence, *he is like most artists: a lot of virtuosity and not a drop of sincerity*.

Tasks:

Team up in pairs.

Make up questions for the text.

State the main idea of the passage in one sentence.

Learning objectives: to understand the general content of the text, defining keywords and phrases,

formulate questions about the content of the text and answer them, make a plan for the key words.

ACT 2. Compare (5 minutes)

Read the fables of I. Krylov "The Quartet" and "The Nightingale and the Donkey" expressively.

Questions and tasks:

What did Krylov want to say with fables about art? Find words in the text that convey the idea of the author.

Draw a Venn diagram. Pair up and highlight the common and the different in the diagram.

Discuss. Pick the best answers. Please rate.

Learning objectives: to determine the main idea of the text based on questions, evaluate the statement (monologue / dialogue) in terms of its relevance to the proposed topic / situation, compare the content and topic of the texts.

ACT 3. (10 minutes)

Read the text. Pay attention to the highlighted words.

He will never *sacrifice himself* to another. He thinks only of music, and everyone knows that art is *selfish*. However, it must be admitted that some of his trills are amazingly beautiful. The only pity is that there is no sense in them and they are devoid of *practical significance*.

Questions and tasks:

Explain the meaning of the word "sacrifice" using the example of the sacrifice rites.

What sacrifice rites from your native culture and the culture of other peoples are familiar to you?

How do you understand the meaning of the expression "sacrifice yourself to another"? Give examples.

Why did the Nightingale sacrifice himself to the Student?

How do you imagine Nightingale?

Learning objective: to determine the main idea of the text based on the questions.

ACT 4. Playing roles (8 minutes)

Compose the dialogue and role-play the scene between the Student and the Daughter of the Professor using quotes. Spectators assess the actors' play. They answer the questions: "How did you see the Student and the Daughter of the Professor?" and "How did the author depict them?"

Learning goal: to determine the main idea of the text based on questions, create a statement (description, narration).

Comparative study of the fairy tale by O. Wilde and A. Pushkin

When studying Lukomorya, it is important to draw the students' attention to the nature of the magic. Hence such *questions and tasks*.

Imagine the plot of a fairy tale in the picture. What do you depict in the foreground? What do you depict in the background? Why?

Describe miracles. In what fairy tales have you come across a description of these miracles? Name these tales and their authors.

Has anyone read the fairy tale "Ruslan and Lyudmila"? What miracles and magical objects are found in this tale?

On the other hand, it is important to note that the prologue to the fairy tale "Ruslan and Lyudmila" ends with the inclusion of the author. Questions can be aimed at differentiated work in multi-level groups to complete tasks of varying degrees of complexity.

Team up in groups.

1 group. Read the author's words expressively. How do you imagine it?

2 group. Compose a story from Pushkin the author in prose.

3 group. Introduce yourself as an author. How would you finish the prologue to the fairy tale "Ruslan and Lyudmila"? Enter your wonders and other magical heroes.

"The Tale of the Priest and His Worker Balda"

When do people use the word "balda"? Find synonyms for this word.

Why did Pushkin name the worker Balda? Describe the actions of the hero and the ending of the tale. Why do you now think Pushkin named the worker Balda?

Who sees Balda as stupid, a person who can be easily deceived?

What are the characters in the fairy tale who see in the worker a gullible, naive person?

Vocabulary work with the name of the priest can have several forms, depending on the level of preparedness of the class.

1. Look in the dictionary for the meaning of the word "oily" In Kazakh cuisine, it corresponds to "talkan". What do you know about the preparation method and useful properties of the product?
2. Pay attention to the pictures (see Figure 8-10). Which of the characters are the drawings associated with? How does the author feel about this hero? Prove it.

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

3. Find synonyms for the expression "oily forehead", based on these pictures. Test yourself with a dictionary. "A thick forehead is a forehead filled with oat flour." Explain the expression of Pushkin, which he used as the name of the character. Draw a verbal portrait of the priest and give examples from a fairy tale to support your idea.

As a consolidation of the material, you can offer such questions and tasks.

Why do you think an employee has a name, but a priest has not got? How do you understand the meaning of the hero's name?

Draw on the mental map in the form of a chain of heroes: who deceived whom? Keep the sequence of events in Pushkin's tale.

Select and write down in a notebook three key words for the images of Balda, priest, devil.

Unite into three groups.

1 group. Storytellers. Tell us what the tale is about. Use quotes.

2 group. Commentators. Tell us what makes a fairy tale funny?

A comparative study of a fairy tale can be based on a comparison of the forms of the author's manifestation in the work and humor (as a language game and a reflection of the national paradox). The task is divided into two stages. The first stage is to compare the theme and ideas of the writers' tales. Suggest filling in empty fields in the table (working with solid / non-continuous texts), adhering to the wording in one sentence.

O. Wilde Fairy tale theme	A. Pushkin Fairy tale theme	O. Wilde The idea of a fairy tale	A. Pushkin The idea of a fairy tale

The second stage is the comparison of the author's attitude to the heroes. Using examples for words from the list: compassionate, ridiculed, delighted - to answer which of the heroes the author relates to and why, to justify the position. The proposed tasks help to see in the adventurous nature of the plot the main difference between the paradox of Pushkin's fairy tale and Wilde.

Conclusion

Designing a lesson matrix from the standpoint of achievable measurable results and an algorithm for the student's educational activity contributes to the practical task of teaching the subject, develops in the student an idea of the skills he aspires to master. The effectiveness of the lesson is ensured by a combination of all types of speech activity. The development of the student's linguistic competencies requires, the inclusion of grammatical topics in the lesson within the key episodes of the fiction being studied. Motivation of schoolchildren to study a second language and literature is facilitated by the

differentiation of types of educational activities and their combination, the use of strategies of semantic reading - understanding, analysis, interpretation. It is important to design exercises with the inclusion of elements of predicting the content of the text, to use the assessment of students' responses as an element of learning, which contributes to the development of critical thinking and creativity. Comparative study of literature is aimed at identifying the commonality and differences in the style of writers and understanding the unity of the genre.

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